

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE ANALYSIS OF MONGOLIAN EDITORIAL PRACTICES ON ADDRESSING JOURNALISM ETHICS ISSUES

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Abstract

In this paper, the authors emphasize the importance of the role of the media in improving the self-regulation of Mongolian journalism ethics. The criterion for assessing the quality of the editorial-level code were developed based on the role of the editorial-level code of ethics, the strengths and weaknesses of the editorial code, and the factors to be considered in its development. Within the framework of that criterion, an analysis of the editorial code of ethics of the Mongolian media was conducted. Furthermore, a survey of journalists also highlighted the focus on journalism ethics at the editorial level. As we hypothesized, our research shows that the Mongolian media outlets does not pay enough attention to ethical issues at the editorial level.

Keywords: journalism ethics, self-regulation, criterion for editorial-level codes, role of the professional code of ethics, editorial level codes.

Although, Mongolian national journalism began in 1913, attention to journalism ethics began much later, in the late 1980s. Because until this time, Mongolia had been striving to build a socialist society, Mongolian journalism had a top-down system, or the voice of the authorities, so there was no basis for the development of independent and free journalism. Thus, in the late 1980s, when the climate for socialist transformation began to take shape and the winds of democracy began to blow, industry associations began to discuss the ethics of journalism.

In 1989, the Second Meeting of the Confederation of Mongolian Journalists approved the "Principles of Professional Ethics for Mongolian Journalists", which was the first deontological document to define the professional ethics of Mongolian journalists. However, in 1990, Mongolia transitioned to a free economy and a democratic society and eliminated all forms of media control. As a result, the issue of journalism ethics has been forgotten for a while, with the emergence of the yellow press period, where everyone wants to publish newspapers and chase profits and scandals. After some time, however, the issue of cleansing journalism inside was raised, and in 1996 the Confederation of Mongolian Journalists and the Mongolian Free Democratic Journalists' Union re-approved the "Mongolian Journalists' Professional Code of Ethics". In 2003, at the conference of the Mongolian Association of Free Democratic Newspapers, "Principles of Journalism Ethics"; in 2005 and 2011 "Principles of Professional Ethics for Mongolian Journalists" were approved by the III and XV Congress of the Confederation of Mongolian Journalists. Various associations have developed codes and principles five times to regulate ethical issues in the

field of journalism, but there wasn't enough effect. Researchers have attributed this to the lack of media self-regulation mechanisms.

In 2015, the Mongolian Media Council (MMC) was established on a voluntary basis by journalists to regulate the ethics of the sector. However, the emerging MMC alone, which has more than 500 media outlets with a population of only three million, cannot fully address the issue of ethics in journalism.

We hypothesized that the high number of ethical mistakes in journalism was due to a lack of attention to ethical issues at the editorial level. Thus, more than 100 journalists were surveyed on how their editorials address ethical issues, how they adhere to their code of ethics, and how they deal with ethical mistakes. We also collected codes of ethics from 75 media outlets and analyzed the codes they developed through certain criteria.

The basis of self-regulation of journalism ethics is a code of professional ethics. Principles of professional ethics are defined as "guidelines and recommendations that summarize the basic concepts of professional ethics, are aimed at improving professional performance, and require mandatory adherence"¹. The code, a systematic set of guidelines for standard moral, is a document that prohibits certain types of behavior that are considered unethical and defines other types of behavior as ethical. It is important to pay attention to its role, requirements, development practices, and adherence to it, as adhering to the code of professional ethics that underpins its regulation will help reduce the likelihood of recurrence and improve future work.

One. The practice of addressing journalism ethics at the editorial level

¹ Choisamba Ch. Journalist ethics mistakes. Ulaanbaatar. 2004. P12.

A survey of 110 journalists surveyed how their media organizations focused on journalism ethics and how it was managed at the editorial level. 54.5% of the respondents are journalists working for news websites, 23.6% for television, 13.6% for newspapers, 5.5% for radios and 2.7% for magazines.

62.7% of them work for private media outlets, 22.7% for media outlets belonging to certain groups,

10.9% for public media outlets, and 3.6% for government media units.

37.3% of the respondents said that editorial did not introduce the code of ethics when they were first hired, while 25.5% said that they should look at the code of professional ethics. In the remaining 37.3%, the organization's human resources and management have fully introduced the code of ethics.

Fig 1. Responses for question "Does your media organization have a code of ethics".

When asked if your media outlet has a professional code of ethics, 39% said "Yes. It has a code of ethics that reflects the specifics of the organization's operations". 5.5% said they did not have a code of ethics and 11.8% said they did not know if they had an editorial code. 25.5% of respondents said that their editorial office adheres to the code of the MMC, while 18.2% follow the code issued by the Confederation of Mongolian Journalists. However, when the MMC was established in 2015, the Confederation of Mongolian Journalists revoked its code of ethics and transferred its responsibility for sector ethics to the council. Thus, 18.2% of the respondents answered that the invalid code is still valid. This means that 30% of respondents do not know whether the media outlets they work for have a code of ethics.

110 responses

Fig 2. Responses for question "How well do you know your editorial code of ethics".

When asked "How well do you know your editorial code of ethics?", 60% of respondents said that they know the principles of ethics. 23.6% answered they knew only partially, 10.9% said they had never read it,

and 6.4% said they did not know at all. This shows that 40.9% of the respondent journalists are not fully acquainted with the code of ethics.

Fig 3. Responses for question “How often does your organization update its editorial code of ethics”.

When asked “How often does your organization update its editorial code of ethics?”, half of the 110 journalists said they did not know if they were updating. 13.6% said they had not updated their code for

more than five years, and 10% said they had not updated at all. This shows that 73.6% of editorials do not update their code and have not updated for a long time.

When asked if editorial takes feedback from journalists when updating code of ethics, only 29.1% said they do.

Fig 4. Responses for question “How well does your editorial office adhere to its code of professional ethics”.

When asked “How well does your editorial office adhere to its code of professional ethics?”, half of the respondents said they follow it regularly. 26.4% said it was used only when there is ethical issues, while 16.4% said it was just a slogan, but did not discuss compliance.

7.3% said that although there is a code, it is not considered in ethical decision making. Of these, 23.7% reported that they did not use the code at all in making ethical decisions.

Fig 5. Responses for question “How do you decide professional ethics dilemmas”.

51.8% of journalists said that they had a difficult ethical dilemma while working somehow. However, when faced with ethical issues, only 33.6% adhere to their code of ethics. Most of them decide with their

management (50.9%), colleagues (44.5%) and friends (9.1%). 27.3% said they solve problems on their own, while 24.5% read textbooks on professional ethics to

solve problems. This shows that a significant percentage of journalists seek to be responsible in dealing with complex ethical issues. However, the editorial code of

ethics does not specify who to turn to in such situations and who to talk to, so they decide on their own or with friends.

Fig 6. Responses for question "How does your editorial staff react when a journalist makes a professional misconduct".

When asked "How does your editorial staff react when a journalist makes a professional misconduct", only 30.9% said that a journalist discusses a case as a team, as explaining to his/her colleagues why he/she made an ethical mistake. Only 3.6% said they would add to their code of ethics how to deal with similar issues in the future. This is a very poor indicator.

Unfortunately, 40.9% said that if a journalist made a mistake, the chief staff would meet with the journalist separately and issue a warning. 6.4% said that the chief staff directly blames the journalist. It can be seen that management staffs are working in an ineffective way, directly blaming and punishing, instead of discussing and learning about ethics in the community.

Even worse, 11.8% said that a journalist's ethical misconduct is only discussed when it is publicly criticized, 15.5% do not know if it was an ethical mistake unless someone has complained, and 4.5% says that the editorial office ignores the journalist's mistake. It can be seen that 31.8% of the editorial chief staffs does not pay attention to ethical issues at all.

Two. Analysis on editorial code of ethics.

In order to analyze editorial codes and verify their quality, specific criteria for editorial-level codes should be developed. To do this, we must first consider the role of the professional code of ethics and the factors to consider when developing the code.

The main functions of the code of professional ethics can be defined as ideological (1), regulatory (2), judicial (3), and educational (4). It should be noted that the order in which these functions are discussed below is not intended to reflect the degree of their importance.

Ideological role: The code of professional ethics proclaims the values and principles of the profession to members of the professional group and to the public. Thus, the professional ideas embodied in the charter not

only create a sense of tradition and unity among the members of the group, but also help to develop the moral values and high standards of the professional organization². For example, the ethical documents of international journalistic organizations state that a journalist's ethical shortcomings will be judged by his or her colleagues, reflecting the group's views on professional solidarity. In practice, adherence to the principles of professional ethics helps to build a foundation of public trust and, consequently, professional privilege and independence³. It is clear that public confidence in journalism can be enhanced by the declaration and implementation of the idea that journalism serves the public and should therefore be ethical. Furthermore, having a code of ethics is considered an important professional attribute, and the professional ideas contained in the code of ethics can symbolically promote the professionalism and legitimacy of a group⁴.

Coordinating role: It is important to maintain professional standards, as unethical actions by a journalist can damage a professional's reputation. The code provides a code of ethics for media professionals to maintain ethical standards. On the other hand, professional ethics in journalism reduces the need for external regulation and makes professional behavior predictable and accountable⁵. The codes in editorial and union ethics help to regulate the relationship with the recipients by creating an expectation in the public that the industry will exercise its authority responsibly, independently and collectively.

Jurisdiction role: A professional code of ethics is the real basis for judging a journalist's actions as right or wrong. Based on the code, the journalist's actions can be discussed and judged. On the other hand, it allows the individual to compare his or her own ideas with those of the group.

² Kuitgen, J. Evaluating codes of professional ethics. In W. L. Robison, M. S. Pritchard, & J. Ellin (Eds.), *Profits and professions: Essays in business and professional ethics*. Clifton, NJ: Humana Press. 1983. P255.

³ Heermance, E. L. *Codes of ethics*. Burlington, VT: Free Press Printing Co. 1924. p1.

⁴ Kuitgen, J. The ideological use of professional code. *Business and Professional Ethics Journal*. 1(3), 1982. p53-69.

⁵ Kintner, E. W., & Green, R. W. Opportunities for self-enforcement of codes of conduct: A consideration of legal limitations. In R. T. De George & J. A. Pichler (Eds.), *Ethics, free enterprise, and public policy*. New York: Oxford University Press. 1978. pp248-263.

Educational role: Through professional codes, professional members can be instructed on behaviors learned by their predecessors who have succeeded in avoiding or resolving ethical issues related to their field⁶. Some professionals may not agree or understand because they do not know professional ethics⁷. However, finding that there is an accepted code of ethics by a professional group can influence their adherence. According to Kuitgen, the ultimate value of the code is that it motivates professionals to think about the ethical implications of their work, rather than just providing recipes⁸. Defining the educational significance of the code, Milesco-Pitel said, "It is rare for people to be forced to engage in moral behavior. Instead, they can be trained by informing them of the ethical issues they face on a daily basis. That way, they have a good idea of what their morals are"⁹. A well-established code of ethics helps media professionals to make ethical decisions in practice and to develop a sense of professional ethics.

Limitations and Weaknesses of the Code of Professional Ethics: Although the Code of Professional Ethics offers possible tools for shaping professional behavior, it has some shortcomings in terms of its role.

First of all, the code should not apply to everyone. "No rules or guidelines should cover all situations of conflict of interest, or be expected to dictate behavior in a variety of situations that may arise"¹⁰. Thus, the code can serve as a set of general guidelines for professional behavior. As a result, the individual cannot escape the influence of expert choice and judgment.

Another weakness of codes is their inability to effectively deal with moral conflicts and conflicts of principles¹¹. Behavioral disorders are when an expert knows what to do but does not make the right choice due to lack of willpower, self-interest, or other pressures.

Some scholars have interpreted misconduct from a different perspective, arguing that it is not possible to include ethical norms in employment contracts or to specify liability in ethics, and that the reason for accepting or disregarding professional ethics is a personal matter. John S. Merrill, an American media theorist, puts it this way: "Ethics, on the other hand, is self-determined and self-enforcing. Ethics gives media professionals certain basic principles and norms for judging their actions as right or wrong, good or bad, responsible or irresponsible. Thus, ethics is essentially individual, and law is social in nature. Moral norms are personal

and internal, so they should not be punished from the outside. Therefore, media professionals should seek guidance not only from organizations, commissions and councils, but also from themselves"¹².

However, some researchers have criticized the fact that voluntary compliance with the code of professional ethics has little effect on journalists. According to Hulteng, "Codes without teeth and without an organization to enforce them tend to affect only responsible and ethical professionals. On the contrary, the code of ethics has little effect on those who need it most"¹³. Therefore, unless the code of professional ethics includes sanctions, it does not guarantee a change in an individual's behavior.

Conflict of principles means that two or more principles of the rules conflict with each other, making it difficult for an expert to choose which one to prefer. For example, it is a basic principle for a journalist to report the truth, but this sometimes contradicts the principle of mitigation. Truth be told, in the event of serious harm to the life of an innocent person, a journalist must first consider a code of professional ethics in order to make an ethical decision. However, in most cases it is not possible to specify which codes are more important in the codes, so it is clear that the journalist will make his or her personal choice after further study of other ethical theories and textbooks. "The codes do not address the problem of professional ethics, but only signal that professionals should be aware of such problems"¹⁴.

Another disadvantage of codes is the ambiguity of the wording. For example, the provision that "a journalist must distinguish between advocacy and informational work" can be difficult to implement if it does not elaborate on what an advocacy work is.

The disadvantage is that the interests of the association take precedence, as most professional members are involved in the development of the code of professional ethics. As a result, there are times when ethics is more strictly coded than professional ethics. "Professional rules must recognize professional interests and clarify their limitations"¹⁵ Reeck said. In other words, the code of ethics for journalism is independent and fair because it serves the public. To address this shortcoming, it is recommended that the media, their client groups and the public be involved in the development and implementation of national professional codes.

Factors to consider when developing a code: There are a number of important factors to consider when developing a code of ethics. For example, what is

⁶ Johannesen, J. The ideological use of professional code. *Business and Professional Ethics Journal*. 1(3). 1982. pp53-69.

⁷ Hadley, A. T. *Standards of public morality*. New York: Macmillan Co. 1912. p14.

⁸ Kuitgen, J. The ideological use of professional code. *Business and Professional Ethics Journal*. 1(3). 1982. pp53-69.

⁹ Milesco-Pytel, D. With a dose of morality. *American Education*. 1979. P32.

¹⁰ McGuire, J. M. Conflict of interest: Whose interest? And what conflict? In R. T. De Georsg and J. A. Pichler (Eds.), *Ethics, free enterprise, and public policy*. New York: Oxford University Press. 1978. p 225.

¹¹ Callahan, D. Do special ethical norms apply to professions? In L. H. Orzack & A. L. Simcoe (Eds.), *Professions*

Forum Proceedings. New Brunswick, NJ: Rutgers University Bureau of Educational Research and Development. 1982. p8.

¹² John C. Merrill, Ralph D. Barney. *Ethics and the Press: Readings in Mass Media Morality*. Hastings House. 1975. Pp 8-17.

¹³ Hulteng, J. L. *The messenger's motives: Ethical problems of the news media*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall. 1976. P230.

¹⁴ Campbell, A.V. *Moral dilemmas in medicine*. London: Churchill Livingstone Ltd. 1972. P5.

¹⁵ Reeck, D. *Ethics for the professions*. Minneapolis, MN: Augsburg Publishing House. 1982. P66.

the purpose of the code? How does this relate to your target audience? What should be the structure and content of the code? Should the code be general or very specific? Should the code represent a positive or negative tone? How wide should the code be? How to improve the clarity and meaning of the code? should be noted that. Let me now explain each of the factors to consider when developing a professional code of ethics.

1. The role and purpose of the code

The role of professional code must be understood in terms of its purpose. In other words, whether the code is a call or declaration code or a regulated code depends on the purpose. It also depends on whether the code is used for inspiration, education, or to evaluate the results of one's actions.

Lon Fuller identified two distinct categories of professional code of conduct, one for aspirational ethics and the other for duty ethics¹⁶. According to him, the code of aspiration is positive and aesthetic, and is based more on the highest moral values, such as a better life and the full use of human potential. The codes, on the other hand, are based on the idea that it is impossible to build a law-abiding society without following the rules and regulations of the "you can't" law.

If too much emphasis is placed on ideas in the development of professional rules, the code will obscure the realities of professional practice and norms of practice. But too much emphasis on action is not enough to inspire morality. Therefore, in defining the role and purpose of code development, it is necessary to balance the expression of moral aspirations and the expression of obligations (measures to prevent unethical behavior), which is recognized as a difficult task¹⁷.

Researchers such as Reeck and Harris, on the other hand, have suggested that a code of professional ethics should be described in more general terms, rather than as an instructional or prohibitive function¹⁸. The code, which seeks to explain professional ethics, not only raises ethical awareness, but also provides a more transparent understanding of the public. The advantage of explanatory codes is that they are more flexible and help to make ethical behavior easier to understand, but may not be effective in controlling inappropriate behavior¹⁹. Therefore, a code developed in combination with such guidelines is recommended.

2. Code acceptability

Any guidelines must be accepted and respected by professional members. In other words, the code should not only instruct you to do this and that, but also declare what the profession does, to whom, and for what purpose²⁰. This will help you better understand that the professional mission is related to the roles and responsibilities of the members.

The active participation of members of the professional association in the code development process is very important and will not only improve the content of the code, but also provide an incentive to maximize its acceptance. According to Fulmer, those who follow the rules are more likely to support it if they are involved in its development²¹.

3. Code structure and content

Most codes of conduct consist of an introduction (a), professional ethics, information about values (b), and guidelines related to those principles and values (c). The introduction explains the nature, purpose, scope, and priorities of the code. Explaining the basic principles of professional ethics can be powerful if it is linked to the values of the profession. Also, the advantage of incorporating one or more of the basic principles of professional ethics into the code is that²², first, it provides an understanding of the basic issues of professional ethics; second, they determine what issues need to be addressed as the code of ethics emerges; and third, it prevents the overconfidence that ethical responsibilities will be met unless certain rules are violated.

It is also important to provide guidance on how to implement the basic principles through clear guidelines and prohibitions.

The important thing to pay attention to in the logical structure of the code is to prioritize and define which basic principles are more important. For example, the basic principle of journalistic integrity is that it prohibits journalists from obtaining information in an unfair manner. However, when the principle of journalistic value is enshrined in the first place, it provides a basis for justifying the use of unfair methods in some cases to provide truthful information that is important to the public.

It is clear that the main content of the code of ethics is expressed in its provisions. Therefore, depending on who the provisions are addressed to, it is possible to determine whether the content omits the ethical issues of one of the parties. The code may be addressed to professional members (a), clients (b), other representatives of the profession (c), and the public (d). In the field of journalism, these are journalists and media workers; recipients; sources of information and advertisers; will be affected by the effects of journalism. The same idea was expressed by M.Zulkafili, "The general principles of ethics apply to simple, everyday situations and practices in journalism, and are manifested as rules or prohibitions. It is a journalist-receiver, a journalist-source

¹⁶ Fuller, L. L. *The morality of law*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press. 1969. P5-6.

¹⁷ Levy, C. S. *Professional ethics: Dilemmas of code construction*. Paper presented at the National Conference of Social Welfare, Philadelphia, PA. 1979, May.

¹⁸ Reeck, D. *Ethics for the professions*. Minneapolis, MN: Augsburg Publishing House. 1982.

¹⁹ Harris, C. E. *Structuring a workable business code of ethics*. University of Florida Law Review. 1978. P353.

²⁰ Levy, C. S. In search of a professional code of ethics. *NASW News*. 22(2). 1978. p1 -3.

²¹ Fulmer, R. M. *The new management*. 2nd ed.I. New York: Macmillan. 1978.

²² Kitchener, K. S. Intuition, critical evaluation and ethical principles: The foundation for ethical decisions in counseling psychology. *The Counseling Psychologist*. 12(3). 1984. p43-55.

of information, a journalist-hero of his work, a journalist-author, a journalist-editor, a journalist-editorial team, a journalist-colleague".²³

4. The ratio of general to specificity of the code

Professional association codes are more general than organizational and editorial level codes. This is because the more general the union code, the more flexible it is to define a wide range of roles, responsibilities, and relationships. Rivers, Schramm, and Christians argue that code should be general: "The more intricate the provisions, the more likely they are to become obsolete and limited to what you shouldn't do"²⁴. In our opinion, the communication code is not at the editorial level, so it may be general, but it can create a loophole that intentionally violates it. Therefore, it is important for code developers to maintain an appropriate relationship that is general and specific.

5. Language editing

For the code to be an effective guide, it must be written in a language that is understandable to those who will use the document. It also needs to be explained if it reflects a new concept in the professional field.

Another issue with grammar is the avoidance of overuse of forbidden language. Robert W. Austin, former dean of the Harvard Business School, said about the code of conduct for executives: "Negative language can not only create a positive sense of responsibility in the profession, but can also arouse public suspicion"²⁵. If the amount of negative provisions increases, it is clear that "either you will lose weight by trying to regulate all the behaviors, or you will leave a loophole for inappropriate actions"²⁶. Therefore, it is best to write the code in positive language²⁷. For example, a journalist's statement that he or she will accept or respect their social, religious, sexual orientation, and racial discrimination is a better expression of the language.

The following criteria have been developed to assess the quality of the code of professional ethics from the point of view of ethics researchers on the role of the code of professional ethics, its limitations and weaknesses, the process of its development and the issues to be considered.

1. Whether the professional code of ethics has been developed in the correct order
 - Whether the code update and development requirements are defined
 - Representatives of journalists, researchers, employers and customers were involved in approving the code development commission
 - Whether the Commission has collected and analyzed the rules of international organizations and modern industry codes
 - Whether stakeholders have commented on the draft charter

- Whether the members or their representatives voted unanimously to ratify the charter

2. Whether stakeholder input is included in the development of the Code of Professional Conduct (as a separate criterion as it has a significant impact on content and acceptability)

- journalists / union members
- media outlets
- the public

3. Whether the purpose of the code of professional ethics includes both encouragement, regulation and interpretation

4. Whether the structure of the professional code of ethics is complete

- Does the introduction describe the nature, purpose, and scope of the code?
- Are all the basic principles of professional ethics reflected? These are
 - seek the truth and report the truth;
 - minimize harm;
 - work without conflict of interest;
 - not to use deception, misleading or false methods;

- recognition of differences/inequality;
- principles of respect for privacy.

• Are there clear ways to implement the basic principles of professional ethics?

• Whether sanctions for the implementation of the basic principles of professional ethics are adequately reflected

• Whether the basic principles of professional ethics are logically arranged in order of importance

5. Whether the content of the code of professional ethics is appropriate for general and specific clarity

6. Whether the content of the code of professional ethics reflects the concerns of stakeholders in the field of journalism. These include:

- The core is journalists and media workers
- Consumers
- Sources of information
- Affected by creativity
- Business customers

7. Is the language of the professional code of ethics good?

- Understandable
- Explains ambiguous concepts
- Written in a positive tone

If the above criteria are met, the applicability and acceptability of the code is high.

The code of professional conduct is followed at the individual journalist, editorial, national, regional and international levels. In doing so, it will follow the code of ethics of the editorial board, self-regulatory

²³ Zulkafili M. Journalism research works. Volume XIX. Free press: history, theory, practices. Ulaanbaatar. 2022. p167.

²⁴ Rivers, W. L., Schramm, W., & Christians, C. G. Responsibility in mass communication. New York: Harper and Row. 1980. P143.

²⁵ Austin, R. W. Code of conduct for executives. Harvard Business Review. 22(5). 1961. p59.

²⁶ Harris, C. E. Structuring a workable business code of ethics. University of Florida Law Review. 1978. P315.

²⁷ Johannesen, R. L. Ethics in human communication. Prospect Heights, IL: Waveland Press. 1983. P101.

bodies, unions and international organizations. However, the requirements of the code of professional ethics may differ depending on the level of compliance. For example, if the code of a press council or association is general, the code of ethics for the editorial board should reflect the culture and activities of the organization or be more specific. Therefore, the following criteria have been developed for the editorial level code from the above criteria.

1. It should reflect the specifics of the editorial office
2. Reflect the basic principles of professional ethics
3. The code should be more specific and well-defined than the code of professional associations
4. Indicate the responsibilities and actions to be taken in the event of misconduct
5. Updated regularly
6. Discuss community feedback on code updates
7. Based on community use. To this end, the code of ethics should be shared with the community, and in the event of a complex situation, it should be discussed and resolved by the community in accordance with the code.
8. Be transparent to the public and advertise to the public

We tried to collect the code of ethics from 75 media outlets. Of these, 50 were news sites, 15 were television, 6 were daily newspapers, and 3 were radios. The

following steps were taken to collect the code of ethics for these media outlets.

1. Checked if the media outlet has a transparent code of ethics on its website.
2. Contacted the media outlet that did not have a code of ethics on their website and asked following questions.
 - Does your media have a code of ethics?
 - Do you have your own separate code or do you follow the code of the Mongolian Media Council?
 - If you have a code of ethics, can you share it?
3. The editorial ethical codes are analyzed according to the criteria for editorial level code.

Of the 75 media outlets, 37 (49.3%) said they did not follow any code of ethics. Ten said they had the code, but for some reason it could not be made public or shared with the research team.

The remaining 28 (38.8%), 19 media outlets (25.3%) posted the code of ethics of on their websites. Of these, 13 were codes approved by the MMC, 2 were codes approved by the Confederation of Mongolian Journalists but are no longer valid, and only 4 developed and published their own codes at the editorial level. The remaining nine media outlets reported adhering to the MMC code, but did not publish it on their websites.

Let's analyze the 4 ethical codes currently being developed at the editorial level according to the criteria for the editorial level code.

Table 1.

Indicators how editorial level codes met its' criterions.

№	Criterions to assess editorial level code	Media outlets developed editorial level ethical code			
		Gogo.mn	Unread.today	Ubn.mn	Yolo.mn
		https://gogo.mn/policy	https://unread.today/page/policy	https://ubn.mn/policy	https://www.yolo.mn/policy
1.	It should reflect the specifics of the editorial office	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
2.	Reflect the basic principles of professional ethics	Mostly yes	Yes	Yes	Mostly no
3.	The code should be more specific and well-defined than the code of professional associations	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
4.	Indicate the responsibilities and actions to be taken in the event of misconduct	Yes	No	No	No
5.	Updated regularly	The results of a survey form journalists show that this criterion is met in general, not in specific media.			
6.	Discuss community feedback on code updates				
7.	Based on community use. To this end, the code of ethics should be shared with the community, and in the event of a complex situation, it should be discussed and resolved by the community in accordance with the code.	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
8.	Be transparent to the public and advertise to the public	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

At the editorial level, there are three common shortcomings for media outlets that develop their own code of ethics. First, the code of ethics does not cover all the basic principles of journalistic ethics, but omits some of them. Second, there are no penalties for misconduct. Third, research from journalists shows that the code of ethics is rarely updated on a regular basis due to technological advances and new areas of journalism.

Conclusions: The following conclusions can be drawn from a survey of journalists on how a media organization pay attention to ethical issues and from an analysis of the editorial level codes.

1. There are rare media outlets that have developed their own code of ethics. There are medias that follow the MMC code, but due to it is not an editorial level code, there are some restrictions. For example, there is a general code that does not specify the responsibilities for ethical errors and the specifics of editorial work.

2. The fact that most media outlets do not publicly publish their code of ethics, and some refuse to share it with the research team, is a sign that media outlets do not realize that declaring that they are transparent and accountable has a significant impact on recipients' trust to media and journalism.

3. Editors do not introduce their code of ethics to new employees, and some journalists do not even know if the organization has a code, or are partially familiar with the code, which shows that the media pays very little attention to ethics.

4. Most editors do not update their code, do not update it for a long time, and do not reflect the views of the colleagues in the development of the code. Therefore, at the editorial level, code development and updating should take into account the views of the community and follow the correct steps.

5. Studies show that journalists do not use their codes in their ethical decisions, and that their slogans are mere proclamations.

6. In case of a journalist's misconduct, executives use ineffective methods such as directly blaming the journalist and deducting it from his or her salary, instead of discussing and learning about ethics in the community.

Finally, Mongolian media outlets need to urgently develop editorial level codes of professional ethics which met standard criterions to address journalism ethics issues.

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